

DEVELOPING COMPENSATORY COMPETENCE THROUGH GAMES AND ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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***Abstract.** This article examines the role of games in the system of developmental education in primary school. The game is an effective method that promotes the development of skills, intellectual abilities and social competencies in primary school students. The article presents an analysis of the theoretical foundations and principles of developmental education, and also describes various gaming technologies used in primary school. In addition, the article is based on the results of a practical study conducted with the participation of primary school students. The results obtained confirm the effectiveness of using the game in the system of developmental education and its positive impact on the educational achievements and development of students.*

***Keywords.** Game, developmental education, primary school, skills, intellectual abilities, social competencies, efficiency, game methods, student independence, comprehensive development.*

Introduction. In the modern educational context, the importance of integrating the game into the learning process is increasingly recognized. The game allows children to actively participate, develop their skills and abilities, and also facilitates the assimilation of educational material. Developmental learning is aimed at developing students in all aspects - cognitive, social, emotional and physical. The game is an effective method to achieve the goals of developmental learning, as it stimulates the development of various skills and abilities of students. In primary school, it is especially important to use the game, as children in this They are at the stage of active development and formation of basic skills and abilities.

Main part. In elementary school lessons, various game methods can be used that promote the active participation of students, the development of skills and

abilities, as well as the assimilation of educational material. Here are some examples of game techniques that can be used in elementary school lessons: 1. Role-playing: Students represent various roles and situations, play the roles of characters from literary works or historical events. 2. Quest game: Students solve various tasks and puzzles in order to advance along a certain plot or achieve a goal. This contributes to the development of problem-based thinking, logical thinking and the ability to work in a team. 3. Playing the role of an expert: Students explore a specific topic or problem by acting as an expert. They present their research, make presentations, and answer class questions. 4. Competition game: Students participate in team or individual competitions, they solve problems or answer questions faster than others. It stimulates motivation, develops reaction speed, concentration and competitive spirit. 5. Simulation game: Students simulate certain processes or situations, for example, the creation of their own country or organization. This allows you to develop creative thinking, decision-making and planning skills. At the beginning of the 20th century, American psychologist John Dewey developed the concept of "play as a method of learning", emphasizing the importance of active student participation in the educational process.

Conclusion. Thus, playing in the system of developmental learning in elementary grades is an effective method that promotes the development of skills, intellectual abilities and social competencies among students. It creates a favorable educational environment, stimulates the active participation of students and contributes to their comprehensive development. These are just some examples of game techniques that can be used in elementary school lessons. It is important to adapt game methods to specific learning goals and the age group of students in order to achieve the maximum effect of learning through play.

REFERENCES

1. Casey, A., & MacPhail, A. (2018). Adopting a Models-Based Approach to Teaching Physical Education. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 23(3), 294–310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2018.1429588>.

2. Henriksen, D., Henderson, M., Creely, E., Ceretkova, S., Černochová, M., Sendova, E., Sointu, E. T., & Tienken, C. H. (2018). Creativity and Technology in Education: An International Perspective. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 23(3), 409–424. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-018-9380-1>.
3. McLoughlin, G. M., Graber, K. C., Woods, A. M., Templin, T., Metzler, M., & Khan, N. A. (2020). The Status of Physical Education Within a Nationally Recognized School Health and Wellness Program. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 39(2), 274–283. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2019-0052>.
4. Rotatori, D., Lee, E. J., & Sleeva, S. (2021). The Evolution of the Workforce during the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Human Resource Development International*, 24(1), 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2020.1767453>.
5. Autor, D.H., Dorn, D., and Hanson, G.H., 2013. The China syndrome: Local labour market effects of import competition in the United States. *American Economic Review*, 103(6), 2121-68
6. Balleer, A., Gehrke, B., Lechthaler, W., and Merkl, C., 2016. Does short-time work save jobs? A business cycle analysis. *European Economic Review*, 84, 99-122.
7. Becker, S.O., Egger, P.H., and Ehrlich, M.V., 2010. Going NUTS: The effect of EU structural funds on regional performance. *Journal of Public Economics*, 94(9), 578-90.

THE IMPORTANCE OF REAL-LIFE TASKS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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***Abstract.** This article emphasizes the importance of incorporating real-world tasks into language learning. It highlights how these tasks can improve learners'*